

1 **Direct chromatographic study of the enantioselective biodegradation of ibuprofen**
2 **and ketoprofen by an activated sludge**

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12 **ABSTRACT**

13 The quantification of the enantiomeric fraction (*EF*) during the biodegradation
14 process is essential for environmental risk assessment. In this paper the enantioselective
15 biodegradation of ibuprofen, IBU, and ketoprofen, KET, two of the drugs most
16 consumed, was evaluated. Biodegradation experiments were performed in batch mode
17 using a minimal salts medium inoculated with an activated sludge (collected from a
18 Valencian Waste Water Treatment Plant) and supplemented with the racemate of each
19 compound. The inoculum activity was verified using fluoxetine as reference compound.
20 The experimental conditions used (analyte concentration and volume of inoculum) were
21 chosen according to OECD guidelines. In parallel, the optical density at 600 nm was
22 measured to control the biomass growth and to connect it with enantioselectivity. Two
23 RPLC methods for chiral separations of IBU and KET using polysaccharides-based
24 stationary phases were developed. Novel calculations and adapted models, using directly
25 the chromatographic peak areas as dependent variable, were proposed to estimate
26 significant parameters related to the biodegradation process: biodegradation (*BD*) and *EF*
27 values at given time, half-life times of (R)- and (S)-enantiomers, number of days to reach
28 a complete *BD* and the minimum *EF* expected. The modelled *BD* and *EF* curves fitted
29 adequately the data ($R^2 > 0.94$). The use of these new equations provided similar results
30 to those obtained using concentration data. However, the use of chromatographic peak
31 areas data, eliminates the uncertainty associated to the use of the calibration curves. The
32 results obtained in this paper indicate that an enantioselective recognition towards IBU
33 enantiomers by the microorganisms present in the activated sludge used in this study
34 occurred, being the biodegradation of (R)-IBU higher than that of (S)-IBU. For KET,
35 non-enantioselective biodegradation was observed.

36 **Keywords:**

37 Batch experiment
38 Enantioselective biodegradation
39 Ibuprofen
40 Ketoprofen
41 Chiral separation
42 Peak area based estimates

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48 **1. Introduction**

49 Public environmental awareness has increased notably in recent years, due to the
50 adverse effects that pollutants can produce not only on the environment but also on the
51 human health. Among the emerging pollutants, drugs are probably the main concern of
52 regulatory authorities because of their huge consume. Drugs, their metabolites and their
53 degradation products could reach the environment mainly due to poor removal rates in
54 Waste Water Treatment Plants (WWTP), and by improper disposal of unused medicines
55 [1]. The presence of these compounds in the environment has been extensively reported
56 [2-5]. However, although the great efforts made by regulatory authorities and scientific
57 community, not much is known about the impact of this kind of compounds on the
58 environment and the human health [6-10].

59 The majority of currently available drugs are chiral compounds and, even though
60 the use of single enantiomers has increased during the last decades, many of these are
61 marketed as racemates [11]. As a result of the enantioselective human metabolism, and
62 also of the microbial biodegradation during the wastewater treatment process, these
63 compounds are not present in the environment in their original racemic or enantiomeric
64 form. For this reason, and due to the fact that enantiomers may have different
65 toxicological and ecotoxicological properties compared to each other, the quantification
66 of the enantiomeric fractions (*EF*) during the biodegradation process is essential for
67 environmental risk assessment. However, there is not much research done on this subject.

68 Some studies have been focused on the direct *EF* quantification in WWTP
69 influents and effluents [12-15]. Other approaches have been based on *in vitro*
70 biodegradability assays. The OECD tests for ready biodegradability have been devised as
71 screening methods to determine whether or not a chemical is potentially easily
72 biodegradable. They simulate the degradation processes of chemicals in soils, surface

73 waters or in activated sludge, generally in the presence of oxygen [16]. The subsequent
74 separation and determination of the individual enantiomers of the original compound (or
75 its metabolites) in the test solution by analytical techniques, mainly liquid
76 chromatography, allow the estimation of *EF*. Using this methodology, the
77 enantioselective evaluation of biodegradation (*BD*) for amphetamines [14,17,18], β -
78 blockers [17,19,20] and antidepressants [15,17,19,21,22] have been reported.

79 Ibuprofen (IBU) and ketoprofen (KET) are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory
80 (NSAIDs) chiral drugs with anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities, being IBU one of
81 the most popular clinically used drugs in the world [23]. Their therapeutic effects have
82 been observed to reside almost exclusively in the (S)-enantiomers while the (R)-
83 enantiomers are weakly active or inactive (e.g, (S)-IBU has been reported to be 160 times
84 more active than (R)-IBU) [24,25]. In spite of the differences in their enantiomers
85 activity, IBU and KET are commonly manufactured, dispensed and consumed as racemic
86 mixtures [25].

87 The occurrence of the NSAIDs IBU and KET in WWTP influents and effluents
88 from WWTPs of Spain [26,27], Australia [25,28] and Switzerland [29] has been reported.
89 In these studies, the enantioselective biodegradation was evaluated by comparison of the
90 *EF* values obtained in influents and effluents. (S)-IBU was found to be predominant in
91 wastewater influents due to chiral inversion during human metabolism [25-28] and
92 preferentially degraded during wastewater treatment [27-29]. Matamoros et al. [26], in
93 the evaluation of the biodegradation of IBU in different WWTPs, found high variability
94 on the *EF* values for constructed wetlands, being in the final step of the process (R)-IBU
95 preferentially degraded. The authors attributed this behaviour to the presence of
96 microorganisms and changes in the aerobic and anaerobic conditions in the WWTP could
97 induce the chiral inversion of (R)-IBU to its optical antipode. Moreover, the chiral

98 inversion degree seems to depend on the WWTP considered [28]. For KET, no significant
99 changes in *EF* were reported [25,27].

100 In order to study the enantioselectivity in the NSAIDs biodegradation,
101 experiments under laboratory conditions have also been performed. In a laboratory-scale
102 membrane bioreactor, the (S)-IBU was preferentially degraded, while for KET, a slightly
103 higher degradation of (R)-KET was observed [30]. Buser et al. also found a faster
104 degradation of (S)-IBU during the incubation in the laboratory of an influent from a
105 WWTP containing IBU, with an activated sludge and under aerobic conditions [29].
106 Incubation of lake water fortified with racemic IBU also indicated a faster dissipation of
107 the (S)-enantiomer [29].

108 Changes in the *EF* values during the biodegradation process have been mainly
109 explained by the more rapid degradation of one enantiomer relative to the other (i.e.
110 enantioselective degradation). However, it is well established that 2-arylpropionic acids
111 undergo *in vivo* chiral inversion during mammalian metabolism, and also in several
112 species of fungi and bacteria. Multiple enzymes are believed to play a role in the process,
113 varying the degree and/or direction of chiral inversion in the different organisms [5,28].
114 Therefore, changes in the *EF* for ibuprofen and ketoprofen could be explained not only
115 by enantioselective degradation, but also by chiral inversion or by the concurrence of both
116 processes [5,28].

117 Chiral analysis of NSAIDs in the above-mentioned enantioselective studies was
118 carried out mainly by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry after diastereomer
119 formation with the chiral derivatising reagent (R)-1-phenylethylamine [25,28,30], or
120 using a cyclodextrin-based chiral stationary phase [26,29]. Liquid chromatography-mass
121 spectrometry has also been applied with a (R)-1-naphthylglycine based chiral stationary
122 phase and a mixture of tetrahydrofuran- ammonium acetate in methanol as mobile phase

123 [27]. In the literature, few references exist about chiral separations of IBU and KET in
124 reversed phase conditions [31-36].

125 One aim in this work is to evaluate the biodegradation of IBU and KET
126 enantiomers to provide more information on this issue, ~~In this work,~~ due to the ambiguous
127 results reported in the literature ~~for the biodegradation of IBU and KET enantiomers,~~ For
128 this purpose, a ready biodegradability test (compatible with the OECD guidelines) is
129 performed. ~~For this purpose,~~ Experiments are carried out in batch conditions using an
130 activated sludge inoculum from a local WWTP which receives domestic, agricultural,
131 livestock and industrial wastewater. The inoculum activity is checked using fluoxetine as
132 reference substance. Abiotic assays and biomass growth control assays are also
133 performed. For the separation of the IBU and KET enantiomers, several polysaccharide
134 based chiral stationary phases in RPLC conditions were tested.

135 Another aim in this work is ~~Using IBU and KET~~ to develop a new strategy based
136 on the direct use of chromatographic peak areas of enantiomers (instead of their
137 concentrations) ~~as dependent variables. novel equations are developed~~ to estimate
138 significant parameters related to the biodegradation process such as: *BD* of enantiomers
139 and *EF* values at given time, half-life times of enantiomers, number of days to reach a
140 complete biodegradation and the minimum *EF* value expected. The purposes of this
141 strategy are: (i) to eliminate the uncertainty source associated to the calibration stage and
142 (ii) to reduce the experimental effort and cost due to the elimination of the calibration
143 step. For this purpose, novel equations to calculate and model *BD* and *EF* data based on
144 peak areas as dependent variables are developed. The results obtained are compared with
145 those obtained using conventional calculations/models and with previous reported results
146 for biodegradation of IBU and KET enantiomers.

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148

149 **2. Material and methods**

150 *2.1. Chemicals and solutions*

151 Racemic Ibuprofen (*rac*-IBU), (S)-(+)-ibuprofen ((S)-IBU), racemic ketoprofen
152 (*rac*-KET) and (S)-(+)-ketoprofen ((S)-KET) were from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO,
153 USA). Fluoxetine hydrochloride (FLX) was kindly donated by Alter (Madrid, Spain).

154 All reagents were of analytical grade. Formic acid (98 %), sodium dihydrogen
155 phosphate monohydrate, sodium hydroxide, acetonitrile (ACN), isopropanol, ethanol and
156 methanol (MeOH) (®Multisolvent, HPLC grade) were from Scharlau, S.L. (Barcelona,
157 Spain).

158 Ultra Clear TWF UV deionized water (SG Water, Barsbüttel, Germany) was used
159 to prepare solutions. Different solutions were tested for the preparation of the mobile
160 phases. Aqueous solutions of formic acid (0.1 %, v/v, pH 3.0) were prepared. Phosphate
161 buffer (10 mM, pH 8.0) was prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of sodium
162 dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate in water and adjusting the pH with 2.5 M sodium
163 hydroxide. The mobile phases were prepared by mixing 0.1 % formic or 10 mM
164 phosphate solutions with the tested organic modifier to obtain the working concentration.

165 The minimal salts medium (MSM) solution used in the biodegradation assays was
166 prepared with the following composition per litre [19,20]: 2.1 g Na₂HPO₄ (Panreac
167 Química, S.A., Barcelona, Spain); 1.4 g KH₂PO₄ (Panreac); 0.2 g MgSO₄·7H₂O (Scharlau
168 Chemie S.A., Barcelona, Spain); 0.5 g (NH₄)₂SO₄ (Scharlau), and 10 mL of a trace
169 elements solution with the following composition per litre: 2.0 g NaOH (Scharlau); 12.0
170 g Na₂EDTA₂·2H₂O (Scharlau); 1.4 g FeSO₄·2H₂O (Panreac); 1.3 g CaCl₂·2H₂O
171 (Panreac); 10 g Na₂SO₄ (Panreac); 0.7 g ZnSO₄·7H₂O (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany); 0.3

172 g $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panreac); 0.1 g $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck); 0.1 g $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck);
173 0.5 mL H_2SO_4 (98 %) (Scharlau).

174 Activated sludge was kindly donated by General de Análisis Materiales y
175 Servicios, S.L (GAMASER, S.L., Valencia, Spain), a laboratory and inspection entity of
176 the Group “Aguas de Valencia”. It was obtained from the aerated tanks of a municipal
177 WWTP (Quart Benàger, Valencia, Spain), which receives domestic, agricultural,
178 livestock and industrial wastewater from eight Valencian towns with a surface area of
179 164171 ha and a population of approximately 1 million. Its average flow rate is 30318
180 m^3/day . Activated sludge was collected in plastic flasks and stored at 4 °C until usage.
181 The storage of the activated sludge before usage was inferior to 24 h.

182 Stock standard solutions of 1000 mg L^{-1} of *rac*-IBU, *rac*-KET and FLX were
183 prepared by dissolving the adequate amount of each compound in methanol. To prepare
184 the calibration standards, intermediate stock solutions of 100 mg L^{-1} of *rac*-IBU, *rac*-
185 KET and FLX were prepared by dilution of the corresponding 1000 mg L^{-1} stock solution
186 in the MSM. Solutions of 100 mg L^{-1} of *rac*-IBU and *rac*-KET were spiked with 50 mg
187 L^{-1} of the corresponding (S)-enantiomer for the identification of the enantiomers peaks.

188 For each drug, calibration solutions of approximately 2, 5, 10, 20 and 30 mg L^{-1}
189 were prepared by dilution of the corresponding intermediate stock solution of 100 mg L^{-1}
190 in the MSM. For the biodegradability assays, working solutions of approximately 20 mg
191 L^{-1} of *rac*-IBU, *rac*-KET and FLX were prepared by dilution of the 1000 mg L^{-1} stock
192 solution in the MSM. The solutions were stored under refrigeration at 4 °C. The storage
193 time was inferior to 24 h.

194

195 *2.2. Instrumentation*

196 An Agilent Technologies 1100 chromatograph (Palo Alto, CA, USA) with a
197 binary pump, an UV–visible diode array detector, a column thermostat and an
198 autosampler was used. Data acquisition and processing were performed by means of the
199 LC/MSD ChemStation software (B.04.02 SP1 [208], ©Agilent Technologies 2001-
200 2010).

201 For the determination of FLX, an Halo C₁₈ column (2.7 μm, 75 × 4.6 mm i.d.;
202 Advanced Materials Technology, Wilmington, USA) and phosphate buffer (10 mM, pH
203 8.0):ACN (30:70, v/v) mobile phase were used. The injection volume was 2 μL. The
204 detection was performed in the UV at 220 nm. The mobile phase flow rate was 1 mL min⁻¹
205 and the separation temperature 25 °C.

206 For the separation of the IBU and KET enantiomers, several polysaccharide-based
207 chiral stationary phases were tested: Chiralart Cellulose-SC (cellulose tris(3,5-
208 dichlorophenylcarbamate); 3 μm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; YMC Separation Technology Co.,
209 Ltd., Tokyo, Japan); Lux Cellulose-1 (cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate); 3
210 μm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA); Lux Cellulose-3 (cellulose
211 tris(4-methylbenzoate); 3 μm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) and
212 Lux Amylose-2 (amylose tris(5-chloro-2-methylphenylcarbamate); 3 μm, 150 × 2.0 mm
213 i.d.; Phenomenex).

214 For the determination of IBU enantiomers the Lux Cellulose-3 column and a
215 binary mixture of methanol:formic acid aqueous solution (0.1 %, pH = 3) (80:20, v/v) as
216 mobile phase were used. The separation temperature was set at 25 °C and the mobile
217 phase flow rate was 1.0 mL min⁻¹. The injection volume was 2 μL. The detection was
218 performed in the UV at 220 nm.

219 The separation of KET enantiomers was carried out using the Lux Amylose-2
220 column and a binary mixture of acetonitrile:formic acid aqueous solution (0.1 %, pH = 3)

221 (35:65, v/v) as mobile phase. The separation temperature was set at 15 °C and the mobile
222 phase flow rate was 0.5 mL min⁻¹. The injection volume was 2 µL. The detection was
223 performed in the UV at 240 nm.

224 For samples mixtures preparation, 15 mL conical sterile polypropylene tubes
225 (Deltalab, S.L., Barcelona, Spain) were used. Disposable sterile filter pipette tips (Capp
226 Expell, Odense, Denmark) were also used. For the biodegradability assays, a shaking
227 incubator with temperature control (WiseCube® Wis-30, Witeg Labortechnik GmbH,
228 Wetheim, Germany) was used. Prior to the measurement of the microbial growth,
229 incubated samples were subjected to agitation in a vortex mixer (Velp Scientific Vortex,
230 Usmate, Italy). Microbial growth was monitored by measuring the optical density of the
231 cultures at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) with an Epoch 2 microplate reader (Biotek Instruments Inc.,
232 Vermont, USA) and 96-well plates with UV transparent flat bottom (Corning,
233 Kennebunk, ME, USA). Samples were stored at -80 °C in an ultra-low temperature freezer
234 (U570 Premium, New Brunswick Scientific, Herts, UK) until chromatographic analysis.

235 Prior to injection into the chromatographic system, samples were centrifuged
236 (Hettich Lab Technology, EBA 20, Tuttlingen, Germany) and filtered through disposable
237 0.22 µm polyethersulphone syringe filters (Frisenette, Knebel, Denmark). Mobile phase
238 solutions were vacuum-filtered through 0.22 µm Nylon membranes (Micron Separations,
239 Westboro, MA, USA) and were degassed in an Elmasonic S60 ultrasonic bath (Elma,
240 Singen, Germany) prior to use. A Crison MicropH 2000 pHmeter (Crison Instruments,
241 Barcelona, Spain) was employed to adjust the pH of the buffer solutions.

242

243 2.3. Biodegradability assays

244 The biodegradability assays were performed in batch mode at 15.6 ± 0.2 and 18.0
245 ± 0.3 mg·L⁻¹ of *rac*-IBU and *rac*-KET, respectively. These values were the estimated

246 concentrations of racemate solutions as sums of the averaged estimated concentrations
247 for the enantiomers (two independent samples) at $t = 0$, after interpolation in the
248 calibration curves (see Results and discussion section). For the preparation of the samples
249 mixtures, 15 mL uncovered sterile tubes were used. Samples mixtures containing 3000
250 μL of the corresponding working solution of *rac*-IBU and *rac*-KET inoculated with 100
251 μL of the activated sludge (total sample volume of 3100 μL) were prepared. Independent
252 samples were prepared for each compound and each incubation time studied. All
253 experiments were done in duplicate, using tubes of a volume five-fold superior to
254 guarantee the aeration of the cultures. The samples were incubated on a shaking incubator
255 (150 rpm) at 20 °C under natural light cycles. At eight prefixed incubation times (0, 3, 5,
256 11, 18, 21, 25 and 28 days), two test tubes of each compound were taken, and when
257 necessary to compensate solvent evaporation, ultrapure water was added to get a total
258 volume of 3100 μL . Then, mixtures were vortex mixed for 20 s and an aliquot of 200 μL
259 of each tube was taken to measure the OD_{600} of the cultures. After OD_{600} measurement,
260 samples were frozen at -80 °C until HPLC analysis (described in section 2.2). Abiotic
261 degradation of the enantiomers of IBU and KET was evaluated using 100 μL of ultrapure
262 water instead of the activated sludge inoculum, under the same conditions as samples.
263 Prior to HPLC analysis, the samples were centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 15 min and the
264 supernatant was filtered. A similar procedure was used for the biodegradability assays of
265 FLX at 20 mg L^{-1} .

266

267 *2.4. Software and data processing*

268 For modelling purposes, the NLINFIT.m function in MATLAB® R2016b
269 (MathWorks, Natick, Massachusetts) was used. It estimates the coefficients of a nonlinear

270 regression function using iterative least squares estimation. Details of the algorithm for
271 the explicit Lambert W function can be found in [37].

272

273 **3. Results and Discussion**

274 *3.1. Inoculum activity control*

275 The microbial community of an activated sludge in a given WWTP could change
276 over time and, therefore, its biodegradation activity against incoming compounds could
277 also vary. In order to verify the biodegradation capacity of the activated sludge used as
278 inoculum in a laboratory assay for a given compound, a reference substance has been
279 recommended to be tested in parallel [38]. Fluoxetine (FLX, 20 mg L⁻¹) has been
280 proposed as a rapid ‘inoculum activity control’ (unpublished results). Fluoxetine has been
281 chosen according to the results of previous experiments. Briefly, the study implied four
282 inoculum collection dates from the same WWTP, different storage times of the inoculum
283 in the laboratory and three different analysts performing the assay. ~~Concretely,~~ As a
284 result, it was concluded that if the biodegradation (BD) values after seven days of
285 incubation (BD_{7d}) are within the 70 ± 11 % range, the inoculum biodegradation capacity
286 could be considered as normal. In the present case, a BD_{7d} of 69.3 % for FLX was
287 obtained. Therefore, the inoculum activity was considered in the normal range and,
288 therefore, the assays for IBU and KET enantiomers were performed in adequate
289 conditions.

290

291 *3.2. Chiral chromatographic separation*

292 For the separation of enantiomers of IBU and KET, different polysaccharide-
293 based stationary phases (Chiralart Cellulose-SC, Lux Cellulose-1, Lux Cellulose-3 and
294 Lux Amylose-2) were tested (see experimental section). Binary mixtures of formic acid
295 aqueous solution (0.1 %, v/v, pH 3) and different percentages of methanol or acetonitrile
296 were assayed as mobile phases. Experiments were carried out at 15 or 25°C.

297 The use of Chiralart Cellulose-SC and Lux Cellulose-1 stationary phases and a
298 formic acid aqueous solution (0.1%, pH 3):ACN (40:60, v/v) mobile phase, at the
299 temperatures assayed, did not provide resolution of IBU and KET enantiomers.

300 For IBU enantiomers partial or complete resolution was obtained using the Lux
301 Cellulose-3 stationary phase and mobile phases containing different proportions of
302 methanol, (see Table 1). As can be observed, the retention factors and resolution values
303 of IBU enantiomers increased as the amount of water in the mobile phase increased. This
304 fact indicates that the contribution of the hydrophobic interactions to analytes retention
305 and enantioseparation becomes more important in these conditions [39]. With the mobile
306 phases assayed, no reversal in enantiomer elution order was observed. Taking into
307 account resolution and retention times, a mobile phase containing a formic acid aqueous
308 solution (0.1 %, pH 3):MeOH (20:80, v/v) was selected for the separation of IBU
309 enantiomers in further experiments. Under these experimental conditions, adequate
310 retention times (7.3 and 8.1 min for (R)- and (S)-IBU enantiomers, respectively) and
311 resolution ($R_s = 2.3$) were obtained (see Figure 1A chromatogram 2). In the conditions
312 tested for IBU, no resolution of KET enantiomers was obtained.

313 In the case of KET, the use of Lux Amylose 2 stationary phase and mobile phases
314 containing different proportions of ACN at 25°C provided partial resolution of KET
315 enantiomers. It was observed that resolution improved as the separation temperature
316 decreased. As can be observed in Table 1, at 15 °C, the retention factors of KET

317 enantiomers increased as the proportion of the aqueous solution in the mobile phase
318 increased. As for IBU, this behaviour indicates that for mobile phases with high content
319 in water, hydrophobic interactions are important for the retention and the
320 enantioresolution [39]. With the mobile phases assayed, no reversal in enantiomer elution
321 order of KET was observed. Adequate resolution values ($R_s = 1.6$) and retention times
322 (4.1 and 5.2 min, for (R)- and (S)- KET enantiomers, respectively) were obtained using a
323 mobile phase containing a formic acid aqueous solution (0.1 %, pH 3):ACN (65:35, v/v),
324 therefore it was selected for the separation of KET enantiomers in further experiments
325 (see Figure 1B chromatogram 2).

326 In Figure 1A and 1B (chromatograms 1), the chromatogram corresponding to the
327 S-enantiomer was included for identification purposes. As can be seen, for both
328 compounds, the first eluted enantiomer (E1) is the (R)-form while the second one (E2) is
329 the (S)-form. These identifications were also confirmed by the injection of spiked samples
330 with the corresponding (S)-enantiomer.

331 Using the selected experimental conditions, it was observed that concentrations
332 lower than 2 mg L^{-1} of racemic IBU and KET (1 mg L^{-1} of each enantiomer) did not
333 provide adequate peak areas for quantification. So, the peak area at this concentration
334 level was considered as the critical signal for quantification. Details on the calibration
335 statistics are considered in section 3.6.

336 3.3. Biodegradation assays and chromatographic information

337 The biodegradability assays for the enantiomers of IBU and KET were performed
338 in batch mode by duplicate (section 2.3). Sample tubes were collected at different times
339 ($t = 0, 3, 5, 11, 18, 21, 25$ and 28 days) for the biotic and abiotic assays and analysed in
340 the optimal chromatographic conditions.

341 Figures 2A and 3A show the experimental peak area data (A ; mean \pm s from two
342 replicates) obtained during the biodegradability assays for the enantiomers of IBU and
343 KET, respectively. The initial concentration of each enantiomer (S_0) was 7.8 mg L⁻¹ for
344 IBU and 9.0 mg L⁻¹ for KET.

345 Biodegradation, BD , is usually calculated from concentration data (S) obtained
346 over time. ~~Alternatively,~~ in this work a new alternative way to calculate BD directly
347 from the chromatographic information (peak area) is proposed:

$$BD = \frac{A_0 - A}{A_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

348 where A_0 represents the area obtained at $t = 0$. This equation could be obtained from the
349 definition of BD and the linear calibration equation assuming that the intercept of the b_0 ,
350 is statistically non-significant (i.e. confidence interval of b_0 includes zero; see section 3.6)
351 or negligible (i.e. $b_0 \ll A_0$), which is a logical situation:

$$BD = \frac{S_0 - S}{S} \times 100 = \frac{A_0 - A}{A_0 - b_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

352 Figures 2B and 3B show the biodegradation (%) and the standard deviation (BD ;
353 mean \pm s from two replicates) for IBU and KET enantiomers calculated using the Eq. 1.

354 For the IBU enantiomers, during the first days of incubation (from $t = 0$ to $t = 5$
355 days), no degradation was observed (see Figure 2). After this period, the peak areas of
356 enantiomers decreased indicating that a degradation process has occurred, although
357 complete degradation of IBU enantiomers was not achieved at $t = 28$ days. Moreover,
358 higher peak areas were obtained for (S)-IBU enantiomers, which indicates that the
359 biodegradation of (R)-IBU is higher than the one obtained for (S)-IBU (Figure 2B). This
360 suggests that an enantioselective biodegradation by the microorganisms towards IBU enantiomers has

361 occurred. The same conclusion can be derived from the chromatograms shown in Figure
362 1A.

363 For KET, like in the case of IBU, degradation seems to occur after $t = 5$ days (see
364 Figure 3). In addition, complete degradation was achieved after 25 days of incubation. As
365 can be observed in Figure 3A and 3B, similar peak areas and biodegradation values were
366 obtained for both enantiomers, so the degradation of KET by the microorganisms seems
367 not to be enantioselective. These conclusions are in agreement with the observations
368 derived from the chromatograms shown in Figure 1B.

369 For IBU and KET, the abiotic assays (in absence of inoculum) indicated low
370 physicochemical degradation ($< 20\%$). These results indicate that the abiotic elimination
371 of IBU and KET can be considered non-significant [40] and the degradation estimated in
372 the biotic assays can be considered as biodegradation.

373 In order to control the biomass growth during the biodegradation process, the
374 optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600}) during the biotic assays was monitored. OD_{600}
375 measures the solution turbidity and can be considered proportional to the biomass growth
376 [41]. The OD_{600} values for IBU and KET (supplementary data Fig. S1) indicated a
377 biomass growth during the biodegradation process. For both NSAIDs, the maximum
378 biomass growth was observed at $t = 5$ days, followed by a stationary/decline growth
379 phase. In this last phase the differential behaviour for IBU enantiomers was observed.

380

381 *3.4. Biodegradation kinetics*

382 Different kinetic biodegradation models have been proposed in the literature.
383 These models often provide good fit of the experimental data (S and t), despite estimating
384 inaccurate kinetic parameters due to their linear correlation [42,43]. The simplified

385 Monod equation, which resembles a Michaelis Menten equation [44,45], is one of the
 386 most used. It relates S and t by means of the Lambert W function ($S = W \{t\}$, see more
 387 details in the supplementary data; Eq. S2).

388 In this work, this model has been adapted for chromatographic data ($A = W \{t\}$):

$$A = \frac{A_0}{S_0} \left\{ K_s \cdot W \left[\frac{S_0}{K_s} e^{\left(\frac{S_0 - V_m \cdot t}{K_s} \right)} \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

389 where V_m approaches the maximum specific growth rate and K_s is the half saturation
 390 constant for growth (the two parameters to be estimated). By substituting this equation in
 391 Eq. 1 the following equation ($BD = W \{t\}$) is obtained:

$$BD = \frac{100}{S_0} \left\{ S_0 - K_s \cdot W \left[\frac{S_0}{K_s} e^{\left(\frac{S_0 - V_m \cdot t}{K_s} \right)} \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

392 Eqs. 3 and 4, provide estimations of V_m and K_s by non-linear fitting of A vs. t experimental
 393 data. The complete algorithm is provided in supplementary data. To the best of our
 394 knowledge, this is the first time that these expressions have been proposed.

395 Figures 2B and 3B (dashed lines) show the modelled BD vs. t curves according to
 396 Eq. 4, for IBU and KET enantiomers, respectively. The BD data at $t = 0, 3,$ and 5 days,
 397 were excluded for modelling purposes since $BD \sim 0$. As can be seen, the curves fit
 398 reasonably well to the BD experimental points (R^2 values were 0.94 and 0.95 for (R)- and
 399 (S)-IBU, respectively and 0.99 for (R)- and (S)-KET). The extrapolation of the curves
 400 shown in Figure 2B suggests that a complete biodegradation of (R)-IBU would require
 401 around 60 days, while 80 days would be required for complete degradation of S-IBU. For
 402 KET, the biodegradation is complete after 25 days, as stated before.

403 On the other hand, an advantage of modelling BD is the possibility of estimating
 404 the half-life times ($t_{1/2}$). For (R)- and (S)-IBU the $t_{1/2}$ values were 18 and 25 days,

405 respectively, whereas for (R)- and (S)-KET were 12 days. It should be noted that the
 406 quality of the estimation of half-life times provided by Eq. 4 depends on the agreement
 407 between the data and the fitted curves. These $t_{1/2}$ estimates should be less risky than those
 408 based on first-order kinetics (an extra-simplified model of Eq. S2, [44]) usually used in
 409 literature, which could provide inaccurate estimations if the mathematical assumption for
 410 using this model ($S_0 \ll K_s$, [44]) is not confirmed.

411

412 3.5. Enantioselective biodegradation results. Direct chromatographic approach

413 The enantiomeric fraction (EF) at each incubation time was calculated for IBU
 414 and KET enantiomers. This calculation is usually obtained from the concentration data (S
 415 data) of E1 and E2 enantiomers ($EF = S_{E1} / (S_{E1} + S_{E2})$). According to the aim of this
 416 work, an easy way to calculate EF values, directly from the chromatographic information
 417 (peak area), is proposed:

$$EF = \frac{A_{E1}}{A_{E1} + A_{E2}} \quad (5)$$

418 where A_{E1} and A_{E2} represent the area obtained for E1 and E2 enantiomers, respectively.
 419 This equation could be obtained from the definition of EF and the linear calibration
 420 equations for both enantiomers assuming that the slopes ($b_{1,E1}$ and $b_{2,E2}$) are statistically
 421 equal and the intercepts ($b_{0,E1}$ and $b_{0,E2}$) are statistically non-significant (see section 3.6):

$$EF = \frac{S_{E1}}{S_{E1} + S_{E2}} = \frac{(A_{E1} - b_{0,E1})/b_{1,E1}}{(A_{E1} - b_{0,E1})/b_{1,E1} + (A_{E2} - b_{0,E2})/b_{1,E2}} \quad (6)$$

422 In addition, from Eqs. 1 and 5, the following equation can be derived:

$$EF = \frac{100 - BD_{E1}}{200 - BD_{E1} - BD_{E2}} \quad (7)$$

423 where BD_{E1} and BD_{E2} values are the BD values for E1 and E2 obtained from Eq.1. This
 424 expression enables modelling the enantiomeric fraction versus time (EF vs. t) by
 425 combining the BD vs. t fitted curves obtained for the two enantiomers (Eq. 4)

426 Figure 4 shows the experimental mean EF values together with their standard
 427 deviation ($EF \pm s$) obtained at each time during the biodegradation process for IBU. The
 428 horizontal line at $EF = 0.5$ represents no enantioselectivity. In the same figure, the EF vs.
 429 t fitted curve (dashed line) is included. As can be observed, the fitted curve shows a
 430 reasonable agreement with the experimental EF values. For the first days ($t = 0$ to $t = 5$
 431 days), EF values close to 0.5 were obtained that correspond to BD values close to zero
 432 for both enantiomers, as it was previously stated. After that, the EF values decreased to a
 433 value below 0.4 at $t = 28$ days. The EF vs. t fitted curve in Figure 4 allows extrapolating
 434 EF values at higher times. For instance, the EF expected at $t = 60$ days (the time where
 435 (R)-IBU is nearly complete biodegraded) is around 0.2. This value is an extrapolation
 436 which should be taken with caution and will require an experimental confirmation.

437 The results obtained confirm that an enantioselective biodegradation towards IBU enantiomers
 438 by the microorganisms present in the activated sludge used in this study has occurred,
 439 being the biodegradation of (R)-IBU higher than that of (S)-IBU. This enantioselective
 440 biodegradation could be due to several mechanisms: enantioselective degradation, chiral inversion or the
 441 concurrence of both processes. These results agree with those obtained for constructed
 442 wetlands by Matamoros et al. [26] and with the most common behaviour observed in
 443 mammalian and some species of fungi for NSAIDs [28].

444 In the case of KET, as expected according to the previous sections, EF values
 445 close to 0.5 were obtained during the whole biodegradation process (not shown),

446 confirming that its biodegradation process is not enantioselective. This result agrees with
447 those reported in previous studies.

448

449 3.6. Additional remarks

450 *BD* and *EF* estimates were also calculated using the usual expressions based on
451 concentration data (Eq. 2 and 6) for comparison purposes. The calibration curves of each
452 IBU enantiomer were obtained by injection of standard solutions containing racemic IBU
453 in the 2-30 mg L⁻¹ range (5 concentration levels). Table 2 shows the calibration statistics
454 obtained for each enantiomer. As can be observed, satisfactory results ($R^2 = 0.998$) were
455 obtained for both enantiomers. The 95% confidence intervals for the intercepts were $1 \pm$
456 9 and 2 ± 9 for (R)-IBU and (S)-IBU, respectively. This means that in both cases, b_0 is
457 statistically equal to zero; which is the assumption considered in Eq. 1 and 5. Moreover,
458 slopes are comparable according to their confidence interval (10.0 ± 1.0 and 10.1 ± 1.0 ,
459 for (R)-IBU and (S)-IBU, respectively). A *t*-test was also used to compare both slopes
460 [46]. The calculated *t* statistic (0.29) was lower than the critical value, $t_{0.025,8}$ (2.45),
461 indicating the statistical equality of the slopes; which is the assumption considered in Eq.
462 5. When using both *A* and *S*-data as dependent variables, very close values of *BD* and *EF*
463 (at different times) were obtained. The maximum absolute *BD* difference was 2.3 whereas
464 relative differences below 1 % for *EF* were obtained. This indicates that, in general, both
465 strategies could be used indistinctly.

466 However, when using *S* data obtained by interpolation into the calibration curves
467 to calculate *BD* or *EF* data, the uncertainty associated to the interpolation should also be
468 considered. As an example, Table 2 shows the confidence intervals for S_{E1} and S_{E2}
469 estimates obtained by interpolation into the corresponding calibration curves of a peak

470 area $A = 50$. Taking into account the associated confidence limits, the BD values for (R)-
471 IBU would vary between 21 and 54 % (values well below or above of the $t_{1/2}$ level).
472 Therefore, the strategy of using direct A data instead of S as input variables provides less
473 uncertain BD and EF estimations. Similar conclusions were obtained using the statistics
474 for KET.

475 Since the purpose of the current method is not routine sample analysis, but the
476 estimation of the current biodegradation data of IBU and KET, in our opinion, a full
477 method validation seems to be unnecessary, according to the concept of “fit-for-purpose”.
478 Despite this, Table 3 shows some established analytical features obtained for the current
479 methods used. Precision and trueness were investigated with two replicates of spiked
480 solutions at two concentration levels (8 and 1.2 mg L⁻¹) in MSM, which were prepared
481 on five different days. The selectivity was assessed for three biodegradation samples (at
482 $t = 3, 11$ and 21 days) by means an automatic tool for evaluating peak purity of the
483 Chemstation software (section 2.1). Nine spectra per peak provided in all the cases match
484 factor values higher than 995 (over 1000); thus selectivity was considered satisfactory.

485 Finally, adapting accepted protocols used by ISO 17025-accredited laboratories,
486 during the working analysis session (all samples were processed in the same day), one
487 abiotic sample at $t = 0$ was used as a quality assurance stage to control the signal stability.
488 This solution was injected at the start and the end of the working session (as a verification
489 standard) and after each seven sample injections (as a quality control standard), totalling
490 6 times. The relative errors were calculated using the initial peak area values as
491 references. Since all errors were below the ± 10 % prefixed level, it was considered that
492 the peak areas of the biotic and abiotic samples were stable during the session.

493 As internal standard was not used and no standard addition was considered, how
494 were analytical errors compensated for?

495

496

497

498 **4. Conclusions**

499 An enantioselective biodegradability test of ibuprofen (IBU) and ketoprofen
500 (KET), two of the drugs most consumed, was established using an inoculum (activated
501 sludge from a waste water treatment plant) whose activity was verified using fluoxetine
502 as reference compound. IBU and KET enantiomers were monitored using two chiral
503 RPLC methods suitable for samples analysis. As a result of this test (compatible with the
504 OECD guidelines), both compounds exhibited ready biodegradability, with no significant
505 abiotic degradation. In addition, the results indicated that an enantioselective
506 IBU enantiomers by the microorganisms present in the activated sludge used in this study
507 occurred, being the biodegradation of (R)-IBU higher than that of (S)-IBU. For KET,
508 non-enantioselective biodegradation was observed.

509 The biomass growth, indicated by the optical density at 600 nm, confirmed the
510 biodegradation process. For both NSAIDs, the maximum biomass growth was observed
511 at $t = 5$ days, followed by a stationary/decline growth phase. In this last phase the
512 differential behaviour for IBU enantiomers was observed.

513 In this work, new equations to estimate significant parameters related to the
514 biodegradation process -biodegradation (BD), enantiomeric fraction (EF) and half-life
515 time ($t_{1/2}$)- directly from the chromatographic information (peak area, A) have been
516 proposed. The use of these equations provided similar estimates to those obtained using
517 concentration data (S). However, the use of A data as input variable, instead of S ,

518 eliminates the uncertainty associated to the use of calibration curves and should provide
519 less uncertain *BD* and *EF* estimations.

520 Thus, using the new equations proposed some relevant parameters related to the
521 biodegradation process were estimated for IBU and KET: (i) Half-life times of (R)-IBU
522 and (S)-IBU were 18 and 25 days, respectively; while for both KET enantiomers were 14
523 days. (ii) IBU enantiomers required 60-80 days to reach a complete biodegradation, while
524 KET only needed 25 days. (iii) The enantiomeric fraction of IBU decreased to
525 approximately 0.4 at 28 days and the expected minimum value could be around 0.2 at 60
526 days (extrapolated output).

527

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532

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687

688 **Figure captions**

689 **Figure 1.** Chromatograms of (A) ibuprofen (IBU) and (B) ketoprofen (KET) obtained
690 using the experimental conditions detailed in Section 2.2. Chromatogram 1 corresponds
691 to a standard solution of the (S)-enantiomer. Chromatograms 2 and 3 correspond to
692 samples containing racemic mixtures at $t = 0$ and $t = 21$ days of incubation, respectively.
693 Initial racemate concentrations were 15.6 and $18.0 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for IBU and KET, respectively.

694 **Figure 2.** (A) Experimental peak areas (A , mean \pm s from two replicates) obtained for
695 (S)-IBU (○) and (R)-IBU (●) in incubated samples during the biodegradation assay. (B)
696 Biodegradation (BD , %, mean \pm s from two replicates) calculated from peak areas using
697 the Eq. 1 for (S)-IBU (○) and (R)-IBU (●). Dashed lines correspond to the modelled BD
698 vs t curves according to Eq. 4.

699 **Figure 3.** (A) Experimental peak areas (A , mean \pm s from two replicates) obtained for
700 (S)-KET (○) and (R)-KET (●) in incubated samples during the biodegradation assay. (B)
701 Biodegradation (BD , %, mean \pm s from two replicates) calculated from peak areas using
702 the Eq. 1 for (S)-KET (○) and (R)-KET (●). Dashed lines correspond to the modelled
703 BD vs t curves according to Eq. 4.

704 **Figure 4.** Variation of the enantiomeric fraction (EF) of ibuprofen (mean \pm s from two
705 replicates) during the biodegradation assay. EF values were calculated according to Eq.
706 5. Dashed line corresponds to the EF vs. t fitted curve. The horizontal line at $EF = 0.5$
707 represents no enantioselective biodegradation.

708